

Maximum Entropy Random Walk (MERW) and Maximizing Entropy Subject to $\int p(x) dx = 1$

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In previous notes (1), we discussed maximizing Shannon's entropy $-\sum p(x) \ln(p(x))$ subject to a dynamic constraint $\int p(x) dx = 1$. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$, a two dimensional type of probability, which we call dynamic, but nevertheless linked to entropy. $\ln(p(x))$ is then ipx so one must apply the generator of translations d/dx , i.e. make a measurement, to recover p momentum.

In this note we consider MERW (Maximum Entropy Random Walk) theory as outlined in (2). Such a theory is used to create the time-independent Schrodinger equation by considering a kind of stationary equilibrium based on a Maxwell-Boltzman type of transition factor $\exp(-dt/T (V_{xave} + V_{xave+s}))$ for $s=0, +/-1$ where V is a potential, T a kind of temperature and dt an interval in time. This transition factor is used in an average eigenfunction equation:

$$\int W_{xave} = \sum_{s=0, +/-1} \exp(-dt/T (V_{xave} + V_{xave+s})) W_{(xave +s)} \quad ((1))$$

The interesting feature of such an approach is that expanding in terms of dt small leads to $\sum_{s=0, +/-1} \{ 1 + dt (Piece) \}$ with the 1 term actually leading to average kinetic energy (when one subtracts $3W_{(xave)}$ from both sides.. This is quite different from the usual $\exp(iHt)$ evolution operator approach.

In this note, we try to apply ((1)) to the case of no potential, i.e. a free particle, and compare this with the maximization of entropy $-\sum p(x) \ln(p(x))$ subject to a dynamic constraint $\int p(x) dx = 1$.

Quantum Mechanics of a Free Particle

Quantum mechanics of a free particle is usually based on a wavefunction $\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx)$. This measures changes in time and space, but nonrelativistically represents p and $E=pp/2m$ at each x point. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$, which represents directional dynamics because it differs for p and $-p$, is a key difference between classical results.

We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ may be obtained by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to an $\int p(x) dx = 1$ constraint. Thus, one considers an average x with a fixed ip Lagrange multiplier representing dynamic behaviour.

$$\text{Maximize } -\sum p(x) \ln(p(x)) + ipx \int p(x) dx \rightarrow \int p(x) dx = \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ is two dimensional, representing a distribution in position and another in the change in position, we argue. It, however, maps to smooth motion (i.e. All x points carry the same weight) through $\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L} \exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} = 1/L$ where L is length.

We ask: Is it possible to obtain the same results still using entropic ideas, but focusing on a kind of Maxwell-Boltzmann type of equilibrium, i.e. not explicitly using dynamics i.e an $\int p(x) dx = 1$ constraint? We suggest that this may be possible using the MERW (maximum entropy random walk theory) (2).

MERW

MERW is a maximum entropy random walk theory which focuses on the creation of an equilibrium type of distribution, not a dynamic directional scenario like $\exp(ipx)$. Nevertheless, the concept of a wavefunction appears, but is brought in in a mathematical manner.

MERW seems to be largely based on the idea of a transition matrix which allows for motion from x_{ave} to $x_{ave}+s$ where $s=\pm 1$. The transition matrix is given in (2) as:

$$M = \exp(-dt/T) \cdot (V_{x_{ave}} + V_{x_{ave}+s}) \quad ((3))$$

Here V is a potential, T a kind of temperature and dt a tiny interval of time. The operator seems to loosely come from Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics and so represents maximization of entropy. There is a kind of temperature T , but it does not seem to have anything to do with collision kinetic energy as in a MB gas. In addition, dt does not appear in the Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, and it is key in ((3)).

The main idea of MERW (1) seems to be to write an average eigenfunction equation:

$$B W(x_{ave}) = \sum_{s=0,+1,-1} \exp(-dt/T) \cdot (V_{x_{ave}} + V_{x_{ave}+s}) W(x_{ave}+s) \quad ((4))$$

Here B is an eigenvalue and $W(x_{ave})$ is a dominant eigenvector introduced solely through mathematics, i.e. 21) states that it follows from the Frobenius-Perron theorem.

There are two key things to notice in ((4)). First the transition matrix is strictly real (unlike $\exp(iHt)$) and secondly dt is tiny. This allows one to write ((4)) as:

$$B W(x_{ave}) \approx W(x_{ave}) + W(x_{ave}+1) + W(x_{ave}-1) - dt/T \cdot V_{x_{ave}} \cdot 3 W(x_{ave}) \quad ((5))$$

because dt is small one does not include any small variations between $W(x_{ave}+s)$ and $W(x_{ave})$.

In (2), $3W(x_{ave})$ is subtracted from both sides of ((5)) and one multiplies by $-T/3dt$ yielding:

$$T(3-B)/3dt \cdot W(x_{ave}) = T/(3dt) \{W_{x_{ave}-1} - 2W_{x_{ave}} + W_{x_{ave}+1}\} + V(x_{ave})W(x_{ave}) \quad ((6))$$

(2) states that maximization of B means the minimization of $T(3-B)/3dt$ which converges to a number E .

Assuming that $dt=dxdx$ means the term in $\{ \}$ becomes a constant times a Laplacian and one obtains the time-independent Schrodinger equation if E =energy and $C=-1/2m$ nonrelativistically.

$$E W = C \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V W \quad ((7))$$

Quantum Free Particle i.e. $V(x)=0$

We ask in this note whether one may use ((4)) to obtain information about a quantum free particle, i.e. one which is not acted on by $V(x)$. We have already maximized $-P(x) \ln(P(x) + ipx P(x))$ to find $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. a dynamic directional type of probability. $\exp(ipx)$ is stochastic and it requires a measurement, i.e. translational operator d/dx , to find the value of p . If one considers motion in both directions, then energy is $pp/2m$, but there is no specific direction of motion. There should still, however, be stochasticity. Furthermore the idea that $\exp(ipx)$ maps to smooth motion, i.e. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$ suggests that a steady state type equilibrium should also be associated with some kind of smoothness. This smoothness, however, is established in a completely different manner than $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ as shown in ((4)). We suggest that an eigenvalue B multiplied by a function $W(xave)$, should be equivalent to the fluctuations in x , i.e. ((4)) with $V=0$ yields:

$$B W(xave) = W(xave) + W(xave+1) + W(xave-1) \quad ((8))$$

Subtracting again $3W(xave)$ from both sides and multiplying by $-T/3dt$ yields:

$$E W(xave) = C d/dx d/dx W \quad ((9)) \quad (\text{Let } E=\text{energy and } C=-1/2m \text{ nonrelativistically})$$

((9)) is the free particle energy equation which holds for both p and $-p$. $W(x)$ may be direction $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ or a linear combination. Thus, ((8)) is a way of obtaining a steady state stochastic equation. One may note that if E is nonrelativistic energy, then $E=pp/2m$ or p is linked with d/dx . This suggests that $W(x)$ is related to $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, a steady state maximum entropy random walk approach yields $\exp(ipx)$ as does a direct Shannon's maximization of $-P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to the dynamic directional constraint $ipx P(x)$.

We suggest that it is interesting that the two are linked in such a manner.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that MERW (Maximum entropy random walk) for a potential $V(x)$ can be applied to the case of no potential. This approach seems to be a kind of steady state average in which one describes the average $B W(xave)$, where B is an eigenvalue, as being equivalent to the quantity proportional to an average: $W(xave)+W(xave+1) + W(xave-1)$. This may be converted to: $E W = C d/dx d/dx W$ where E and C are constants. If E is nonrelativistic energy and $C = -1/2m$ one obtains the time-independent free particle Schrodinger equation. If $E=pp/2m$, W may be associated with $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ or a linear combination, which applies for a steady state case, e.g. with equal weights, i.e. it is an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$.

We suggest that this maximum entropy approach (because the transition matrix is associated with a Maxwell-Boltzmann type transition: $\exp(- dt/T (Vxave+V(xave+s)))$) is equivalent to directly maximizing $-P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to the constraint $ipxP(x)$. In the latter case, one again has maximum entropy, but considers directional dynamics instead of a steady state picture. It is interesting that $W(xave)+ W(xave-1)+W(xave+1)$ can be transformed into a Laplacian by subtracting $3W(xave)$ and multiplying by a constant.

References

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